

TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF SEPARATING KITS FROM DOES AT DIFFERENT PERIODS AFTER BIRTH

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of a study of the technology of separating rabbits from their mothers at 30, 45 and 60 days after birth and fattening them for 45, 30 and 15 days, respectively, in the rapidly changing climate of Karakalpakstan. Research experiments were conducted during 2021-2023 in the specialized meat direction of rabbit breeding in the Samandar Takhiatosh Limited Liability Company of the Takhiatosh District of the Republic of Karakalpakstan on purebred Californian rabbits. The largest number of rabbits was obtained with the technology of separating rabbits from their mothers at the age of 30 and 45 days. Compared with the technology of separating rabbits from their mothers at 60 days, a total of 87 rabbits were additionally obtained in the technology of separating from the mother on the 30th day, and 40 rabbits on the 45th day. As a result of experiments in the technology of separation from the mother on the 30th day, only 92.3-99.5 kg of rabbit meat was obtained, on the 45th day 44.5-46.9 kg, or from 1 doe 13.2-14.2 and 6.3-6.7 kg of rabbit meat compared to the technology of separation from the mother on the 60th day.*

Keywords: *food security, fodder, oilseeds, rabbit meat, adaptability, clinical, morphological, and hematological indicators.*

Introduction. The "Action Strategy" for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2012-2026 defines key economic development and liberalization priorities. These include the modernization and accelerated development of agriculture, the consistent expansion of agricultural production, further strengthening of the country's food security, increasing the production of environmentally friendly products, and significantly boosting the export potential of the agricultural sector. Additionally, the strategy emphasizes reducing the area under grain crops, increasing the cultivation of potatoes, vegetables, fodder, and oilseeds on the freed-up land, as well as optimizing sowing areas through the establishment of new intensive orchards and vineyards. Furthermore, it highlights the expansion of scientific research and experimental design work to develop and introduce highly productive animal breeds into production [1,2].

The objective of this study is to provide both young and elderly populations with dietary and nutritious rabbit meat and natural leather products, improve the overall nutrition of the population, and enhance economic management by developing rabbit farming across all regions of the country [3].

In Uzbekistan, scientific research on the meat productivity of various rabbit breeds imported from abroad and their adaptability to local climatic conditions has been conducted by researchers such as T. Ikromov, M. Ismoilov, K.I. Khidirov, A. Kholmatov, U. Ballasov, R.I. Ruziyev, D.K. Yuldashev, B. Tojiboyev, F.B. Bakhridinova, B.B. Ibragimov, and others [4-5].

The present study aims to scientifically substantiate the impact of the period of separating kits from does on their productivity, biological parameters, and economic indicators under the conditions of Karakalpakstan.

Research Objectives:

- To study the effect of separation timing from does on the growth and development indicators of kits.
- To conduct a comparative evaluation of experimental rabbit breeds based on key economic traits.
- To analyze the main clinical, morphological, and hematological indicators of meat and blood, as well as exterior traits of the test rabbits.
- To develop rearing, fattening, and separation technology schemes for kits at different time periods.
- To determine the economic efficiency of separating kits at different time intervals.

Development of a Methodological Guide on the Planning and Implementation of Rabbit Rearing and Fattening

Research Object: The object of this study was crossbred kits from local and Californian rabbit breeds, separated from their mothers at the ages of 30, 45, and 60 days.

Research Subject: The subject of the study included indicators of offspring adaptation to changing climatic conditions, as well as aspects of housing, care, and feeding. This involved evaluating growth, development, productivity, exterior dimensions, live weight, and clinical-hematological blood parameters.

Research Methods: The study utilized commonly accepted zootechnical and veterinary methods.

- **Milk productivity and clinical indicators** were assessed using the method of B.G. Menshov.
- **Exterior and body measurements** were evaluated according to the method of E.A. Arzumanyan.
- **Hematological blood parameters** were determined using the "Mindray BC-20s" blood analyzer.
- All numerical results (arithmetic mean, standard error, and significance level of intergroup differences) were mathematically and statistically processed according to the methodology of E.K. Merkur'yeva (1970).
- **Economic indicators** (costs, cost price per kilogram of product, purchase price, net profit, and efficiency level) were calculated using economic formulas.

Results and Discussion: Scientific research experiments were conducted from 2021 to 2023 at the **Samandar Takhiatash LLC**, a rabbit meat production enterprise in the Takhiatash district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The study followed the experimental scheme outlined in **Table 1**. (Table 1 to be included)

Experimental design

Indicators	Groups		
	I	II	III
Number of mothers in the group, heads	7	7	7

Age of separation of kits from mothers, days	30	45	60
Fattening period, days	45	30	15
Housing and feeding conditions	Housing of mothers in individual cages, kits after separation – in common fattening cages		

According to the experimental methodology, three groups of seven female rabbits were formed. During the course of the year-long experiment, their offspring were separated from their mothers at the ages of 30, 45, and 60 days and then fattened for meat for a period of 45 days in the first group, 30 days in the second group, and 15 days in the third group.

In the first and second groups, where kits were separated from their mothers at 30 and 45 days of age, the highest number of offspring was obtained compared to the 60-day separation technology, due to the increased number of litters. No differences were found in the number of offspring taken from each female rabbit.

Table 2

Experimental Results

Indicators	Groups		
	I	II	III
Number of does, heads	7	7	7
Number of kindlings	6	5	4
Total number of kits obtained, heads	265	218	178
Per 1 doe	6,31	6,22	6,35

As a result of the conducted experiments, differences in the physiological cycles of female rabbits were identified under different separation technologies at 30, 45, and 60 days. In particular, it was established that the longer the kits stay with their mother, the longer the resting period, while the pregnancy and lactation periods decrease (see Table 3).

Table 3

Physiological State Periods of Female Rabbits

Indicators	Groups		
	I	II	III
Rest period, days	5	65	95
Gestation period, days	180	150	135
Lactation period, days	180	150	135

The experiments established that increasing the number of litters and reducing the separation period of kits from their mothers weakens the physiological strength of the mother rabbits due to the strain of pregnancy and nursing. This, in turn, negatively affects the rabbit rearing technology.

After fattening the kits until 75 days of age, under the separation technologies of 30, 45, and 60 days, a control slaughter was conducted on 5 rabbits from each group, and their slaughter performance was assessed (Table 4).

Table 4

Slaughter Performance of Kits Raised Under Different Separation Technologies (g, n=5)

Indicators		Groups		
		I	II	III
Pre-slaughter live weight	Minimal	1958,9±1,2	2082,58±1,7	2086±2,7
	Maximal	2116,67±1,4	2136,60±1,5	2262,5±1,6
Carcass weight	Minimal	1061,7±1,0	1104,4±1,7	1138,3±0,9
	Maximal	1144,5±1,2	1173±1,3	1248,9±1,1
Carcass yield	Minimal	52,9	53,0	54,2
	Maximal	54,9	54,9	55,2
Additional meat obtained per doe compared to the 60-day weaning period	Minimal	13,2	6,3	-
	Maximal	14,2	6,7	-

The control slaughter results showed that the best indicators were observed in groups where kits were weaned at 45 and 60 days. However, the overall reproductive potential of rabbits was significantly lower compared to the group where kits were weaned at 30 days.

Specifically, in the group with 30-day weaning, a total of 87 kits were obtained, whereas in the 45-day weaning group, only 40 kits were obtained (compared to the 60-day weaning group). As a result, the additional rabbit meat yield was:

- 92.3–99.5 kg in the 30-day weaning group
- 44.5–46.9 kg in the 45-day weaning group
- Per one doe: 13.2–14.2 kg of rabbit meat per year in the 30-day weaning group and 6.3–6.7 kg in the 45-day weaning group.

The study of body temperature, respiratory rate, and pulse rate of the kits showed no significant differences between the 30-, 45-, and 60-day weaning groups, with all physiological parameters remaining within normal limits. This indicates that the Californian rabbit breed is well adapted to the harsh climatic conditions of Karakalpakstan.

1. In the conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the technology of weaning kits at 30 and 45 days in industrial and domestic settings does not negatively affect their biological characteristics and can be successfully applied.
2. Additional meat yield per doe:
 - At 30-day weaning — 13.2–14.2 kg of rabbit meat
 - At 45-day weaning — 6.3–6.7 kg of rabbit meat
3. Profitability of 9.75–13.11% can be achieved due to increased breeding cycles and higher kit production

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